

First $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ results with a new connection between the EA-IRMS system and the Gas Injection System at CologneAMS

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Abstract

This work presents the integration of an elemental analyzer (EA) and an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (IRMS) into the 6 MV AMS system at the Institute for Nuclear Physics, University of Cologne. The AMS measurement of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values for c6 standard material resulted in $-11.39(226)\text{‰}$, compared to $-10.28(32)\text{‰}$ obtained by IRMS. The EA-IRMS system was also tested with c3, c5, and c7 standards, yielding $-24.79(9)$, $-25.18(15)$, and $-14.76(18)\text{‰}$ respectively. To investigate an observed sample mass dependency, environmental samples from Spitzbergen were examined, showing $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of $-25.17(55)$, $-25.80(31)$, and -26.17‰ in Cologne, while Hamburg recorded $-24.8(1)$, $-25.5(1)$, and $-26.2(13)\text{‰}$. In summary, this new setup enables on-line analysis and quasi-simultaneous measurements of ^{14}C , $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ for ultra-small samples, utilizing precise $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values from IRMS for fractionation correction of the $^{14}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ isotopic ratio.

Keywords: Accelerator Mass Spectrometry, Gas Injection System, Elemental Analyser, IRMS

1. Introduction

At CologneAMS, it is possible to measure CO₂ samples with masses as low as 2 μg (1). This is achieved by oxidizing the sample within an elemental analyzer (EA) and then directing it, using the gas injection system (GIS), to the AMS ion source without the need for graphitization steps.

To meet the increasing demand for ¹⁴C/¹²C isotopic ratio measurements of ultra-small samples (1-20 μg), improvements in isotopic fractionation correction are necessary to enhance measurement accuracy and address dating challenges in archives with low carbon content. Fractionation effects can occur during various stages of the AMS measurement, including sample preparation and oxidation, negative ionization during the sputter process, and stripping process (2), (3), (4). While AMS can directly determine δ¹³C values, one study suggest that values derived from IRMS exhibit greater precision, up to two orders of magnitude (5). Furthermore McIntyre et al. (2016) investigated the international atomic energy agency (IAEA) standard c6 with a literature δ¹³C value of -10.80±0.47 ‰ (6) and demonstrated an improvement in the δ¹³C value from -12.17±2.24 ‰ measured by AMS to -10.50±0.02 ‰ measured by IRMS (7).

Motivated by these findings, a new system has been installed at CologneAMS, which combines the EA and IRMS with the existing Gas Injection System (GIS). This enables the determination of δ¹³C values using the IRMS instead of the AMS. During sample oxidation, around 10 percent of the CO₂ is directed to the IRMS for a δ¹³C measurement, while the remaining gas is directed to the GIS. From the GIS, the sample can be transferred to the HVE SO-110 B ion source, which was installed in 2015 (8). Additionally, this setup will allow for simultaneous IRMS-AMS measurements of gaseous AMS samples from glass ampoules, which are cracked within the GIS.

2. Experimental Setup

The setup consists out of four components. The first is the EA, where samples are oxidised and transferred to the second component, the IRMS. Samples are analyzed for their nitrogen and carbon content in the EA while the IRMS measures the δ¹³C or δ¹⁵N values. From there the sample is captured in the syringe of the GIS, where it can be led into the ion source of the AMS.

2.1. EA and IRMS

For combustion, all solid samples are placed in cleaned tin boats and then oxidized in the EA (vario isotope select by Elementar). By introducing O₂ into the combustion reactor of the EA, the sample undergoes oxidation and becomes gaseous. Helium is used as a carrier gas to transport the sample throughout the system. Within the reduction tube, NO and NO₂ are reduced to N₂, while other combustion products are filtered out.

After exiting the reduction tube, the gas is separated using thermal programmed desorption (TPD). CO₂ is captured at approximately 38°C, while the Nitrogen gas reaches the thermal conductivity detector (TCD) of the EA. The TCD signal provides a peak area indicating the concentration of the incoming gas components. The TCD is calibrated using standards with known concentrations. Once the nitrogen has passed through, the TPD unit is heated to 210°C, causing the release of CO₂, which is then detected by the TCD.

The IRMS (isoprime precisION by Elementar) comprises an ion source that generates positive ions, an electromagnet for momentum separation, and an electrostatic analyzer (ESA). The nitrogen and carbon gases reach the ion source of the IRMS, where they undergo ionization through electron interaction. The positive ions are directed into the electromagnet, and masses 44, 45, and 46 for CO₂ and 28, 29, and 30 for N₂ are separated. They are individually detected in three Faraday cups.

2.2. Gas Injection System

The GIS (Gas Injection System) is a well-established component of the setup at CologneAMS. Its purpose is to capture CO₂ gas from the EA using a zeolite trap and subsequently release it into a syringe. Inside the syringe, the CO₂ gas is mixed with helium before being transferred to the AMS ion source. The zeolite trap used in this setup has a capacity of up to 1000 µg of carbon. Further details of the GIS can be found in (9), (10), (11).

2.3. Connection between EA-IRMS and AMS

This section provides an overview of the newly installed hardware and software connections that link the EA, IRMS, and AMS systems. There are two possibilities to connect these systems. Fig. 1 illustrates the general layout of the two setups. In Fig.1 i), the connection is shown, where samples are

oxidized in the EA and a percentage of the gas is transferred to the IRMS, while capturing the rest in the GIS. Fig. 1 ii) shows the pathway for sample gas which was cracked and then captured in the syringe of the GIS. A portion of the gas can be led to the IRMS, while retaining the remainder for a measurement with the AMS.

For the software connection the EA and the IRMS can be controlled via an application programming interface (API). The API sends out the requests to start or stop a measurement and also collects the incoming data from the various components. The API allows the gas injection control software (GICS) (9) to communicate with the IRMS, this way the GICS software can fully control the measurement.

For samples combusted in the EA, the EA and IRMS are connected via

Figure 1: The schematic diagram illustrates the connection between the EA, IRMS, GIS, and AMS systems. In i), the connection is established for a sample which is oxidized in the EA. Subsequently, the gaseous sample is transferred through a capillary to a T-piece. Around 10 percent of the sample is directed towards the IRMS through a capillary (cyan) for measurement, while the remaining portion is further transferred to the GIS for subsequent analysis in the AMS ion source. Fig. 1 ii) depicts the setup for pre-existing gaseous samples that can be cracked within the ampoule cracker of the GIS. The cracked sample is then transferred to the IRMS under a continuous flow of helium. This is accomplished by splitting an existing capillary, which supplies helium to the GIS, using a T-piece and an additional capillary (red).

1/16-inch diameter tubing. The oxidized sample is transferred through this tubing. A T-piece creates a split, and an additional capillary with a 0.005-inch inner diameter is attached, leading to the IRMS inlet. This setup allows approximately 10 percent of the sample to enter the IRMS inlet for IRMS measurement, while the remaining portion is directed to the GIS. This is visualized in Fig. 1 i). From the EA inlet, the sample gas flows towards a cold zeolite trap, where CO₂ is captured. Once all the CO₂ is inside the zeolite trap, it is heated to 450°C, allowing the CO₂ gas to diffuse into the syringe.

To enable the measurement of pre-existing gaseous samples, an additional connection has been established between the GIS and the IRMS. In future applications, CO₂ samples in glass ampules will be cracked using the GIS ampule cracker, and the resulting gas is transferred to the syringe. A small percentage of the sample gas can be directed into the IRMS, while the remaining gas is retained in the syringe for analysis using the AMS setup. Continuous helium flow is necessary for the operation of the IRMS ion source as the carrier gas for CO₂, as depicted in Fig. 1 ii). The capillary responsible for conveying CO₂ from the GIS to the IRMS is equipped with a T-piece, through which helium is introduced. To achieve a low helium flow, a capillary (red) with a 0.005-inch inner diameter is connected via a T-piece to the main helium line, which also supplies the GIS.

The introduction of CO₂ into the IRMS is accomplished using an open split. The GIS includes a GIS outlet #2 with a tubing of 1/16-inch diameter, which is inserted into the GC capillary of the IRMS. A piece of plastic is placed around the open split and heated. As the plastic shrinks, it secures both capillaries in place.

3. First test measurements - EA and IRMS

This section provides an overview of the measurements conducted on different standard materials and environmental samples using the EA and the IRMS. It should be noted that the EA-IRMS setup was not connected to the GIS or AMS for these measurements.

3.1. IRMS Standard Samples

Various standard materials were oxidized in the EA, and their $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values were determined using the IRMS (see Tab. 1). The initial tests utilized the following standards from the IAEA: c3, c5, c6, as well as c7 and c8. The literature $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of these standards are provided relative to the Pee Dee belemnite scale (6).

Over a three-month period, samples of each standard weighing between 0.030 mg and 2.000 mg were analyzed. This extensive range of sample sizes was chosen to thoroughly evaluate the oxidation process in the EA and the results of the IRMS. Each set of standards underwent at least two measurement sequences, and no reactor changes were made throughout the analysis.

Figure 2: i), the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of c3, c5, and c7 are presented as initially calculated. These data points exhibit a mass dependency, which is addressed by applying a linear fit (shown as a dotted line) for correction. In Fig. ii), the corrected data is displayed. To calibrate the data, measurements from c6 and c8 are utilized.

Table 1: The measured $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values, along with their corresponding standard deviations, are compared to the literature values provided by the IAEA. The IAEA literature values are denoted as $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{PDB}$, representing their expression relative to Pee Dee belemnite (PDB). The data obtained in this work is presented as $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{Cologne}$.

Standard	c3	c5	c7
$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{PDB}[\text{‰}]$	-24.91(49)	-25.49(72)	-14.48(21)
$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{Cologne}[\text{‰}]$	-24.79(9)	-25.18(15)	-14.76(18)
number of samples	31	72	72

Fig. 2 i) presents the results of the measured $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values for the standards c3, c5, and c7, calibrated using c6 and c8 as reference standards. Notably, it was observed that samples with masses exceeding 1.300 mg led to current saturation in the IRMS Faraday cups. Consequently, the application is limited to samples weighing up to 1.300 mg.

The results, depicted in Fig. 2, indicate a mass dependency in the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of all three standards. To address this issue, a linear fit was applied to the data, resulting in the following fit equations: c3: $y_{c3}(x) = 0.4298 \cdot x - 0.1232$, c5: $y_{c5}(x) = 0.4020 \cdot x + 0.0720$, and c7: $y_{c7}(x) = 0.1247 \cdot x - 0.3494$. To correct for this mass dependency, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values are transformed in a way that after transformation the linear fit of the data results in a slope of zero. The corrected values are illustrated in Fig. 2 ii). Tab. 1 shows the standard deviations of the corrected $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values.

This mass dependency was also seen for a similar set of measurements of three additional standards. The mass dependency in Fig. 2 could be interpreted as a dependency to the carbon content, with a lower $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value the slope becomes less steep. However, this effect could not be confirmed with the additionally measured standards not shown in this work.

Comparing the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of the IAEA standards with those measured at Cologne, it is found that they fall within the expected range, with statistical uncertainties below 0.2 ‰. This demonstrates a good and reproducible agreement with the IAEA literature values. Additionally, it is worth mentioning that the careful selection of calibration standards is crucial. In this study, two standards were chosen, which proved to be sufficient for larger $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ ranges. However, for a more precise calibration technique, Coplen et al. (12) can be utilized.

3.2. Samples from Spitzbergen, Norway

In addition, environmental samples COL5115, COL5111, and COL5119 collected from Spitzbergen, Norway, were analyzed for their $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values. These samples had previously been measured at the Institute of Soil Science, University of Hamburg, and are labeled as $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{HH}$. Prior to analysis, the environmental samples underwent decalcification using phosphoric acid, following the method described by Rethemeyer et al. (2019) (13). The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values were measured using a Delta V instrument (Thermo Scientific) (14). Each environmental sample was subjected to two measurements using the new setup. Detailed $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values and their corresponding errors are provided in Tab. 2.

A total of 81 samples were analyzed, ranging in sample masses from 0.060 to 1.300 mg. The samples underwent oxidation in the EA using a helium flow rate of 250 ml/min, and their $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values were determined in the IRMS using standards c3 and c6 for calibration. It is worth noting that the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of the COL samples are similar to each other, indicating that the calibration procedure using only two standards was sufficient for all three samples. However, it is important to exercise caution when calibrating the IRMS system

Figure 3: The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of three environmental samples collected from Spitzbergen are presented. These values are compared to measurements from Hamburg, represented by the red line. Furthermore, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values have been corrected for their mass dependency, and the corrected data is depicted in black.

Table 2: The measured $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values and carbon content of the environmental samples from Spitzbergen, along with their corresponding standard deviations, are presented. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{HH}$ values represent the measurements conducted in Hamburg, while the data obtained in this study are provided as $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{Cologne}$.

Sample	COL5119	COL5115	COL5111
$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{HH}[\text{‰}]$	-24.8(1)	-25.5(1)	-26.2(13)
$\delta^{13}\text{C}_{Cologne}[\text{‰}]$	-25.17(55)	-25.80(31)	-26.17(77)
Carbon content [%]	1.3(14)	1.62(67)	2.9(12)
number of samples	35	23	23

for samples with significantly different $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values to ensure accurate results within each range.

Furthermore, the carbon contents of the samples were determined using the EA and are listed in Tab. 2. Unlike the standards, only the environmental sample COL5115 exhibited a noticeable mass dependency, which was subsequently corrected for. This correction is illustrated in Fig. 3.

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of the COL samples have a larger standard deviation compared to those of the standard material.

Additionally, it is important to acknowledge that the mass dependency effect is not yet fully understood and requires further investigation. To minimize potential errors associated with the mass dependency, future measurements will employ samples and standards with similar $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values and masses.

3.3. $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values for Atacama samples

Environmental samples from the Atacama desert in Chile were analyzed for their $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values and compared to measurements conducted at the University of Bonn using an already established EA-IRMS system. The system in Bonn utilizes a Thermo Fisher Scientific Flash EA 1112 series, which is connected to a ConFlo III interface and a Delta V Advantage IRMS.

For the analysis, the samples were weighed at approximately 200 mg in both institutes and measured alongside N1 ($\delta^{15}\text{N} = +0.43\text{‰}$) and N2 ($\delta^{15}\text{N} = +20.41\text{‰}$) standards to calibrate the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values. The environmental samples exhibit very low nitrogen content, averaging at 0.03 percent. Due to the low nitrogen content, larger sample sizes were required compared to standard

carbon samples.

The first test series in Cologne was conducted on three different days of two weeks, during which the EA reactors remained unchanged. The samples were measured in ascending order based on their names. Each data point represents the average of approximately three samples of the same sample material. A more detailed listing can be found in Tab. 3. Fig. 4 i) presents a comparison of the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values obtained in Cologne and Bonn. The data indicates a discrepancy towards lower $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values for the samples measured last (Loa10, Loa11, Loa12). Further investigation revealed that these samples were only partially oxidized, likely accounting for the observed differences in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values.

To test this hypothesis, a second series was conducted in reverse order, starting with the Loa12 sample and proceeding in descending order of the sample names. This second test series is depicted in Fig. 4 ii). The samples were measured on two different days without changing the reactors, and the O_2

Figure 4: The two test series of the Atacama environmental samples are shown. The first test series, i) were measured in ascending order of the samples names. The second test series, ii), the samples were measured in descending order and with an extended O_2 window during the combustion in the EA. This is done to ensure the full combustion of the samples. The errorbars show the standard deviation of the individual set of samples. If the data point does not have an errobar, only one sample was measured. The identity line is depicted as a dotted line in the figures, serving as a reference.

Table 3: $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of environmental samples from the Atacama desert measured with the EA-IRMS system at CologneAMS.

Sample	First test series		Second test series	
	# of samples	$\delta^{15}\text{N}[\text{‰}]$	# of samples	$\delta^{15}\text{N}[\text{‰}]$
Loa1	3	5.07(27)	2	5.22(40)
Loa2	4	5.72(23)	1	4.15
Loa3	4	4.22(112)	1	4.40
Loa4	2	2.66(255)	1	-1.50
Loa5	3	1.78(61)	1	1.36
Loa6	3	-0.09(63)	2	0.92(490)
Loa7	3	1.12(112)	1	6.90
Loa8	3	-0.28(65)	2	-0.8(100)
Loa9	2	2.32(25)	1	3.64
Loa10	3	-0.34(119)	2	4.04
Loa11	3	1.07(131)	2	3.86(250)
Loa12	3	1.04(21)	2	-3.88(575)

window for combustion was extended from 80 s to 100 s. Due to limited sample material, most of the samples in the second test series could only be measured once or twice.

The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values in the second series exhibit greater scattering compared to the first series, likely due to the low number of measured samples and the heterogeneous nature of the soils. Additionally, it can be observed that the scattering no longer depends on the order in which the samples were measured, indicating that the deviation is now independent of sample order. The results of the first test series demonstrate that this setup is capable of reliably measuring $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values from environmental samples, and the results are comparable to those from other institutes. However, the test series emphasize on a careful execution of the combustion, to ensure that unknown or large sample are fully oxidised.

The standard deviations of the sample material, in comparison to the standards, show an increase. While the standard deviation of the N_2 standards is 0.08 ‰, the samples exhibit standard deviations of up to 2.5 ‰. This difference may be attributed to the non-homogeneous nature of the samples and

warrants further investigation with a larger sample size. The effect could also stem from an incomplete reduction of NO_x to N_2 , but the chromatograms of m/z 28 did not show any abnormalities. Overall, Fig. 4 i) illustrates that the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values obtained from the new setup largely exhibit good consistency with the results from Bonn University.

4. First test measurements - Connection

In this section the two setups shown in Chap. 2.3 are tested with standard material.

4.1. GIS to IRMS

The connection between the GIS and the IRMS was assessed by introducing varying masses of Ox-II gas into the system. The Ox-II gas is a mixture consisting of 5 percent Ox-II and the remaining portion being helium. The carbon mass was determined by measuring the pressure within a known volume of syringe, tubes, and fittings (9). The bottled Ox-II gas was directly transferred to the syringe of the GIS. Target carbon sample masses of $0.50\ \mu\text{g}$, $0.75\ \mu\text{g}$, $1\ \mu\text{g}$, $2\ \mu\text{g}$, $3\ \mu\text{g}$, $4\ \mu\text{g}$, $5\ \mu\text{g}$, $6\ \mu\text{g}$, $7\ \mu\text{g}$, and $8\ \mu\text{g}$ were transferred from the GIS syringe to the IRMS. Four measurements were conducted for each mass, and the average $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value was plotted against the mass in Fig. 5. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ measurements were calibrated using the $8\ \mu\text{g}$ Ox-II sample.

The test of the connected GIS and IRMS system, shown in Fig. 1 ii), yielded reliable $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values with small errors, except for carbon masses below $2\ \mu\text{g}$, where the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values exhibited scattering.

The data points above $2\ \mu\text{g}$ exhibit a standard deviation of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values ranging from 0.03 to 0.06 ‰, except for the $5\ \mu\text{g}$ and $7\ \mu\text{g}$ samples which have standard deviations of 0.19 ‰ and 0.16 ‰, respectively.

For sample masses below $2\ \mu\text{g}$, deviations from the literature value become more significant, potentially due to constant contamination. In this setup, the deviation from the literature value can reach up to $\pm 0.6\ \text{‰}$. Although the standard deviation for the $0.5\ \mu\text{g}$ and $0.75\ \mu\text{g}$ samples is $\pm 0.2\ \text{‰}$, this would still result in reliable $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ measurements, if the calibration gas volume is

kept the same as the sample gas, but it would result in larger errors.

Further testing of this setup is necessary to determine if the deviations from the literature value are caused by constant contamination. The data collected thus far is not sufficient to draw definitive conclusions.

Additionally, as depicted in Chap.3.1, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of solid samples analyzed using the EA-IRMS display a dependency on sample mass. In contrast, the gaseous samples discussed in this chapter do not exhibit such a dependency. It is important to highlight that the sample masses measured in both setups are comparable, as indicated by the similar peak areas measured with the IRMS. This observation suggests that this effect could stem from either the sample or the EA system itself. Further investigations needs to be conducted to find the cause of the mass dependency.

Figure 5: The graphic shows the test series for the connected GIS-IRMS system. Different sample sizes of Ox-II are transferred into the IRMS and its $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value is measured. The data is calibrated using the 8 μg sample.

Figure 6: Shown are the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of c6 which has a literature value of $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{PDB} = -10.80\text{‰}$. The blue data represents the values measured by the IRMS, while the green is the data measured by the AMS. The dotted lines show the average values respectively and the filled in area is the error of the average.

4.2. EA-IRMS to GIS

This section presents the first results of the combustion of samples in the EA and the quasi-simultaneous measurement of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ with the IRMS and AMS.

In the first test measurement, 32 c6 IAEA standards with a $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value of -10.8‰ were measured using the setup shown in Fig. 1 i). Alongside, eight Ox-II samples and two blank samples were also measured for calibration. All samples had a carbon mass of around $100\text{ }\mu\text{g}$.

The c6 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ obtained from the AMS measurements was corrected using the blank and Ox-II samples, while the c6 data from the IRMS measurements was corrected using the data from the Ox-II samples and two empty tin boats

that were measured as well. The evaluated data is presented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 shows that the AMS measurements of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ have a standard deviation seven times larger than the IRMS data. Additionally, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values obtained from the IRMS measurements fall within the standard deviation of the c6 measured using AMS. This is similar to McIntyre et al. (2016) (7), where the IRMS $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value lies within the given standard deviation.

Reasons for the the more precise $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ could lie within the different ion sources that are used in the AMS and IRMS. But the results presented in this work lie close to another and could give rise to the possibility to use the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ from the IRMS for the fractionation correction. In the future further test will be conducted to find if the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ from the AMS could have an systematical offset compared to the IRMS $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ data.

5. Conclusions

The 6 MV AMS system at the University of Cologne, which is used for routine $^{14}\text{CO}_2$ measurements, has been expanded with the integration of an EA-IRMS system, do enable the quasi-simultaneous measurement of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$. The entire system is now computer-controlled using a single software.

While the mass dependency found in Chap. 3.1 needs to be further investigated to find its origin, standard materials and environmental samples consistently yield reproducible $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values that are compareable to the results reported by Knoblauch et al. (2013) (14). Additionally, a good agreement was observed between the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values of Atacama environmental samples measured using the new EA-IRMS system and those obtained from the established EA-IRMS system at Bonn University.

Furthermore, our tests demonstrate that the new EA-IRMS-GIS system allows for the transfer of gaseous samples from the GIS to the IRMS. While this setup is still in progress and requires further testing, the initial measurements of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values have been reliably obtained with sample masses as low as 2 μg . However the measurement of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of samples below 2 μg need to be treated with caution.

As an initial step, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of c6 standard material was successfully measured using both the IRMS and AMS. This system enables precise measurements of a small amount of sample gas for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values while the rest is transferred

to the AMS system. Eventually, this development could enable the use of IRMS $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values to correct for fractionation in AMS measurements.

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